

Identifying scenarios of economic change in rural Scotland

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Background: The Scottish Government funds a programme of strategic research through the Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services (RESAS) Division to advance the evidence base in the development of rural affairs, food and environment policies.

One of the themes of the research programme is on Rural Futures. This theme has three research topics: rural communities, rural economy and land reform. There are two projects within each topic led by Scotland's Rural College and the James Hutton Institute. This publication sits within this theme. Within the rural economy topic, the two projects are:

- *Informing a socially and spatially just future for the Scottish rural economy: pinpointing opportunities, assets and support needs*
- *Novel insights on Scotland's rural and island economies*

The first project, led by the James Hutton Institute, aims to use mixed methods to create an advanced, holistic understanding of the Scottish rural economy and the diversity of responses to multiple crises and events across rural Scotland, in the context of national objectives to deliver a wellbeing economy and longer-term challenges of inequality and depopulation. We aim to identify and inform better interventions and approaches to local development which can enable positive changes in communities. This project will produce evidence, including written publications, open datasets, and online material available to all.

Summary

- **Work Package 3 of the James Hutton Institute's research project has the aim of developing, discussing and refining both plausible and aspirational scenarios of the future of the rural economy of Scotland.**
- **The aim of this note is to firstly outline plans for upcoming research in this Work Package and the main activities which will contribute to this. These include a 'desk based' review of policies and strategies which are likely to impact the rural economy, synthesis of recent data collected from rural communities as part of living labs, and engagement with stakeholders, which will contribute to the co-creation and finalisation of scenarios.**
- **The note also describes proposed parameters and guidelines for the first of these activities, which set out key resources that will be analysed to formulate scenarios of rural economic change.**

Introduction

Research on the rural economy at the James Hutton Institute being undertaken as part of the Scottish Government's Strategic Research Programme 2022-27 is seeking to create new evidence on holistic economic development in rural Scotland. To date, the project is achieving this in three ways:

- Long-term community engagement in living labs, situated in rural areas across Scotland, which have identified recent lived experiences in terms of jobs, local economic benefits, the cost-of-living crisis, local opportunities and assets, and emerging economic issues.
- Identification of the factors which influence decisions made by individuals over places to live, transport and food, through modelling which has quantified the economic value placed on different characteristics, by people within different types of households across mainly rural Scotland.
- Identification of the assets and resources which are recognised as enabling wellbeing-focused economic development in rural Scotland, and their spatial distribution, which will move towards an assessment of changing geographical inequalities and accessibility.

These activities are developing valuable evidence of attributes of rural development in their own right, but they will also support the development of an advanced ('agent based') model which will aim to simulate multiple processes to identify how different places in rural and island Scotland could change between now

and 2050. This change could be measured in terms of key outcomes (for example, population levels and structures, and numbers of jobs) in business-as-usual conditions, as well as in the event of significant developments affecting Scotland and its rural areas, including the implementation of policies and strategies. These insights, the ways that changes in outcomes overlap with existing opportunities and challenges in rural Scotland, and the availability of modelling for further use, could form novel and highly valuable information and resources. To enable this to happen, future economic changes to be introduced to the modelling process need to be responsive and relevant to the developments which are emerging in rural communities, and the strategies and wider policies which are being implemented at different levels of governance.

[A proposed mixed-method framework for identifying scenarios of economic change](#)

Scenarios can be defined as “the stories of... multiple futures, from the expected to the wildcard” (Bishop et al., 2007: 5), potentially covering “descriptions of possible future states and descriptions of developments” (Börjeson et al., 2006: 723). In this project, scenarios will be outputs of modelling from a starting point (c. 2024), with starting conditions reflecting plausible or aspirational situations.

When considering scenarios of economic change in rural Scotland, we suggest that three different factors are particularly relevant:

- The **temporal scale**: scenarios can capture the impacts of long-term trends, and short-term events.
- The **spatial scale**: changes affecting the economy can do so across the whole of Scotland and all of its rural areas, or be more restricted to certain geographical regions, or types of rural area (for example, islands).
- The **purpose** of scenarios, which can form a) predictions, which consider the effects of likely changes, b) explorations of the impacts of hypothetical changes and actions, and c) consideration of how priorities and goals can be achieved (Börjeson et al., 2006: 725-9).

Table 1, below, shows the valuable mixed data and resources which can be used to triangulate scenarios of future economic change within this research. Drawing on the three characteristics of scenarios highlighted above, we aim to identify the broader, nationwide trends which are likely to influence rural development in Scotland in the period to 2050, as well as examples of regional changes and localised interventions.

Plausible, relatively likely changes in rural Scotland will be assessed using a review of recent academic and grey literature, which will identify the most important drivers of rural economic change, and their potential implications for outcomes (e.g. numbers of jobs and rural population levels). Additionally, examples of recent and emerging localised developments, interventions and opportunities are being observed as part of community engagement in the place-based living labs, for instance:

- Increasing tourism based on cruise ships noted in the Western Isles, potentially enabled by new harbour developments.
- New funding streams from renewable energy developments: both from large windfarms, and smaller community-owned schemes, and new engagements between communities and offshore wind developers
- The opening up of land and infrastructure to support employment and business opportunities
- The direct and indirect impacts of the classification of Highly Protected Marine Areas on rural economies and communities

The impacts of these and other changes can be better understood through observations in ongoing living labs, and can contribute to the starting points of plausible scenarios of development. Identifying learning from the living labs will take place as part of Activity 3.1. The hypothetical successful upscaling of these changes to several rural places in Scotland, in ways which maximise their overall benefits, can also form

aspirational, favourable futures which could result from successful enabling policies and developments in governance. Additionally, researchers in JHI-E1-1 have been involved in large-scale data collection as part of the 2020 and 2023 Scottish Islands Surveys, and these survey datasets and published statistics (Wilson et al., 2021; forthcoming information to be published in 2024) form highly valuable resources for understanding changes in local economic development, jobs, services, housing and other characteristics of Scotland’s island regions, which can inform plausible scenarios.

Aspirational scenarios can also be informed by the targets, goals and aims of published strategies and policies, which can include those of the UK and Scottish Governments, regional development and planning organisations (South of Scotland Enterprise, Highlands and Islands Enterprise, National Parks), and the aims of Regional Growth Deals, as examples, and a structured review of these will be carried out (Activity 3.2).

Finally, discussions with stakeholders (Activity 3.3) can finalise the plausible and aspirational scenarios to be considered and included within modelling and ensure their relevance to policy goals, and also capture further insights into regional and national economic changes.

Table 1: Five sets of resources which can be used for identifying economic scenarios

Resources	Type of scenario	Spatial scale, <i>potential information source(s)</i>
1. Critical drivers of rural change (D emographic, E conomic, P olicy, E nvironmental, S ocietal, and T echnological types) and their likely impacts on rural development	Plausible	National <i>Review of the academic and grey literature on the six drivers of rural change in column 1</i>
2. Experiences and perceptions of rural change by rural residents	Plausible	Regional and local <i>Living lab learning Scottish Islands Survey (2020, 2023)</i>
3. The goals and targets of policies and strategies affecting rural development	Aspirational	National and regional <i>Review of the policy and economic landscape</i>
4. Place-based activities and interventions in communities, extended across multiple rural places	Aspirational	National and regional <i>Living lab learning</i>
5. Experiences and perceptions of rural change among national and regional stakeholders, and finalising scenarios	Plausible and aspirational	National and regional <i>Stakeholder consultation</i>

Key parameters of the review of the policy and economic landscape

We envisage that the ‘desk based’ review of policies and economic changes which are likely to affect rural development and jobs will focus on two key resources, shown as points 1 and 3 in Table 1:

- Evaluation of critical drivers of rural change, described within peer-reviewed literature and technical reports. The DEPEST categories of ‘macro-trends’ affecting places (Demography, Economy, Policy and governance, Environment, Society, Technology) has been applied successfully in rural scenario planning (Piras et al., 2022, drawing on work by Aguilar, 1967) and provides a clear framework and structure. Scientific and data-driven evaluations of these drivers can form the basis of “plausible” or realistic scenarios.
- Policies and strategies of the UK and Scottish Governments, and other relevant organisations, which may affect numbers of jobs and development in rural areas. For the purposes of our research, the goals, aims and benefits of these can be considered as “aspirational”, and the policy instruments defined (market-based, regulations, strategies, information campaigns, etc.) would represent the drivers of change to initialise our ‘agent-based’ simulations.

Questions to be answered by the review will be worded closely to points 1 and 3. We intend to build on the work carried out in a Horizon 2020 project, RELOCAL¹, which analysed the literature to develop papers reflecting the six DEPEST drivers of rural change (Demography, Economy, Policy and governance, Environment, Society, Technology), and to update this research for the context of the UK and Scotland in 2024. This update will be implemented through a targeted literature search using the Web of Science Core Collection, specifying a “post-COVID-19” timespan and the inclusion of “the UK” or “Scotland” as search terms. Literature searches are likely to use the Abstract and Author Keywords fields. Additional reading on these drivers will be identified through snowballing, until a point where data saturation is reached and limited new insights are being revealed. Identified drivers can be specified as continuums between different positions (for example, a “decarbonisation of transport” driver could range between extensive uptake of electric vehicles and expanded public transport, to an abandoning of these targets) with the most likely paths identified.

The accompanying review of grey literature will focus on the policies and strategies published recently by multiple nationwide and regional organisations which could be pertinent to rural economic development, and their stated aims and objectives. These are likely to include the UK and Scottish Governments, regional development and planning bodies (Highlands and Islands Enterprise, South of Scotland Enterprise, the Cairngorms and Loch Lomond and the Trossachs National Parks), and strategies and publications of Regional Growth Deals. This review will identify targets and claims of economic development at the national and regional scales. The key metrics and information accompanying these, potentially including the numbers of jobs supported or created and evidence of industries or places which are likely to benefit and/or receive investment, and other aims or ‘aspirations’ of relevant interventions, will be recorded in a structured format. A ‘SWOT’ (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis approach will be used to record potential outcomes. Favourable or aspirational scenarios can be developed from an assumption that these policies and interventions are implemented in a successful way.

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¹ The EU Horizon 2020 research project “Resituating the local in cohesion and territorial development – RELOCAL” (<https://relocal.eu/>, 2016-2021) aimed to identify the impact of place-based interventions on social and spatial justice based on 33 case studies of local contexts across Europe, most of them from rural areas. The James Hutton Institute led the Work Package “Coherence and Scenarios”, which assessed the effectiveness of interventions in the context of different future scenarios. As such, the project is extremely relevant for JHI-E1-1 both methodologically and in terms of topic addressed.

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